

Rac-3i

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-71-RAC-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	4	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 3 71 RAC
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	100.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	1/18/2022 10:12:16 PM CST		
Date Processed:	1/18/2022 10:25:04 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.353	2118644	50.24	191398
2	7.357	2098140	49.76	166017

Asy-3i (DyKAT)

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-72-3-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	106	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 3 72 3
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	100.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	1/18/2022 9:55:01 PM CST		
Date Processed:	1/18/2022 10:26:50 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.368	401223	3.74	39594
2	7.372	10321746	96.26	807319